

On Solving the Ternary Surd Equation

$$(x + \sqrt{x}) + (y + \sqrt{y}) = (z + \sqrt{z}) + k(k + 1)$$

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Abstract

The transcendental equation with three unknowns given by $(x + \sqrt{x}) + (y + \sqrt{y}) = (z + \sqrt{z}) + k(k + 1)$ is studied for obtaining its non-zero integer solutions.

Key words:

Transcendental equation, Surd equation, Ternary surd equation, Integer solutions.

Introduction:

The subject of Diophantine equation, one of the interesting areas of Number Theory, plays a significant role in higher arithmetic and has a marvellous effect on credulous people and always occupies a remarkable position due to unquestioned historical importance. The Diophantine equations may be either polynomial equation with at least two unknowns for which integer solution, are required or transcendental equation involving trigonometric, logarithmic, exponential and surd function such that one may be interested in getting integer solution. Most of the Diophantine problems solved by the researchers are polynomial equations.[1-13]. Note that, the transcendental equation can be solved by transforming it into an equivalent polynomial equation. Adhoc methods exist for some classes of transcendental equations in one variable to transform them into polynomial equations which then might be solved. Some transcendental equation in more than one unknown can be solved by separation of the unknowns reducing them to polynomial equations. In this context, one may refer [14-18].

In this paper, we are interested in obtaining integer solutions to transcendental equation involving surds. In particular, we obtain two different sets of integer solutions to the transcendental equation with three unknowns given by $(x + \sqrt{x}) + (y + \sqrt{y}) = (z + \sqrt{z}) + k(k + 1)$.

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Method of analysis

The surd equation with three unknowns under consideration is

$$(x + \sqrt{x}) + (y + \sqrt{y}) = (z + \sqrt{z}) + k(k + 1) \quad (1)$$

The substitution

$$x = u^2, y = v^2, z = w^2 \quad (2)$$

in (1) leads to the ternary quadratic equation

$$(u^2 + u) + (v^2 + v) = (w^2 + w) + (k^2 + k)$$

On completing the squares, the above equation is written as

$$(2u + 1)^2 + (2v + 1)^2 = (2w + 1)^2 + (2k + 1)^2 \quad (3)$$

Taking

$$2u + 1 = U, 2v + 1 = V, 2w + 1 = P. \quad (4)$$

in (3), we have

$$U^2 + V^2 = P^2 + (2k + 1)^2 \quad (5)$$

Two different methods of solving (5) are illustrated below:

Method 1

Choosing

$$P = \alpha V, \alpha > 1 \quad (6)$$

in (5), we get

$$U^2 = (\alpha^2 - 1) V^2 + (2k + 1)^2 \quad (7)$$

which is satisfied by

$$V_0 = (2k + 1), U_0 = \alpha(2k + 1)$$

Now, consider the Pell equation,

$$U^2 = (\alpha^2 - 1) V^2 + 1$$

whose initial solutions are

$$\tilde{V}_0 = 1, \tilde{U}_0 = k$$

and its general solution $(\tilde{V}_n, \tilde{U}_n)$ is given by

$$\tilde{V}_n = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\alpha^2 - 1}} g_n,$$

$$\tilde{U}_n = \frac{1}{2} f_n$$

where

$$f_n = (\alpha + \sqrt{\alpha^2 - 1})^{n+1} + (\alpha - \sqrt{\alpha^2 - 1})^{n+1},$$

$$g_n = (\alpha + \sqrt{\alpha^2 - 1})^{n+1} - (\alpha - \sqrt{\alpha^2 - 1})^{n+1}$$

Employing the lemma of Brahmagupta between the solutions (V_0, U_0) and $(\tilde{V}_n, \tilde{U}_n)$,

we obtain the sequence of integer solutions to (7) as

$$U_{n+1} = \frac{\alpha(2k+1) f_n}{2} + \frac{(\alpha^2 - 1)(2k+1)}{2\sqrt{\alpha^2 - 1}} g_n,$$

$$V_{n+1} = \frac{(2k+1) f_n}{2} + \frac{\alpha(2k+1) g_n}{2\sqrt{\alpha^2 - 1}} \tag{8}$$

From (6), we get

$$P_{n+1} = \alpha V_{n+1} \tag{9}$$

Substituting (8) & (9) in (4), the values of u, v, w satisfying (3) are obtained.

In view of (2), the integer solutions to (1) are found. It is worth to mention that, for integer solutions, both n and $\alpha (> 1)$ are odd.

Example 1: $n = 1, \alpha = 3$
 $u = 99k + 49, v = 35k + 17, w = 105k + 52$

Example 2: $n = 3, \alpha = 3$
 $u = 3363k + 1681, v = 1189k + 594, w = 3567k + 1783$

Method 2

Write (5) as

$$U^2 + V^2 = [P^2 + (2k+1)^2] * 1 \tag{10}$$

Assume

$$1 = \frac{(4+i3)(4-i3)}{(5)^2} \tag{11}$$

Substituting (11) in (10) and applying factorization, consider

$$U + iV = (P + i(2k + 1)) * \frac{(4 + i3)}{(5)}$$

Equating the coefficients of corresponding terms , we have

$$\begin{aligned} U &= \frac{1}{(5)} [4P - 3(2k + 1)] \\ V &= \frac{1}{(5)} [3P + 4(2k + 1)] \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

The option

$$P = (2k + 1)(5s + 5\alpha - 3) \tag{13}$$

in (12) gives

$$\begin{aligned} U &= (2k + 1)(4s + 4\alpha - 3) \\ V &= (2k + 1)(3s + 3\alpha - 1) \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Substituting (13) & (14) in (4) ,we get

$$\begin{aligned} u &= \frac{U - 1}{2} = k(4s + 4\alpha - 3) + (2s + 2\alpha - 2) \\ v &= \frac{V - 1}{2} = k(3s + 3\alpha - 1) + \frac{(3s + 3\alpha - 2)}{2} \\ w &= \frac{P - 1}{2} = k(5s + 5\alpha - 3) + \frac{(5s + 5\alpha - 4)}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

As the aim is to obtain integer solutions, observe that u , v , w given by (15) are integers when s , α are of the same parity. In view of (2), the integer solutions to (1) are found.

Example 3: $s = 1, \alpha = 3$
 $u = 13k + 6, v = 11k + 5, w = 17k + 8$

Example 4: $s = 2, \alpha = 4$
 $u = 21k + 10, v = 17k + 8, w = 27k + 13$

Note

One may express the integer 1 on the R.H.S. of (10) in general as

$$1 = \frac{[2mn + i(m^2 - n^2)][2mn - i(m^2 - n^2)]}{(m^2 + n^2)^2}, m > n > 0$$

Following the procedure as above, sequences of integer solutions to (1) are obtained.

Conclusion

In this paper, the transcendental equation involving surds with three unknowns given by $(x + \sqrt{x}) + (y + \sqrt{y}) = (z + \sqrt{z}) + k(k+1)$ has been reduced to Pellian equation and polygonal Diophantine equation of degree two with three unknowns for which integer solutions are obtained in an elegant way through suitable transformations and utilizing the technique of factorization. As surd equations are plenty, one may attempt for getting integer solutions to other choices of surd equations with three or more variables.

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